

DeepThought: Should we trust AI with our DNA?

Episode 5 Transcript

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Facilitated by the Atlas of Variant Effect Alliance

Alex Nguyen Ba: In 1997, Deep Blue, a chess machine developed by IBM would defeat the reigning world champion Garry Kasparov in a 6-game match for the first time in what was seen as the pivotal moment in the development of artificial intelligence. The computer, at the time weighed 700 kilograms and stood two meters tall.

Today, the computing chip in your phone would likely never lose against Deep Blue. This progress in computing power and algorithmic design has now solidly taken hold in our daily lives, with recent Nobel Prizes awarded for the development of artificial intelligence. But can scientists harness the power of neural networks for all tasks? Will computers solve the Variants of Uncertain Significance problem? More importantly, would you trust a computational prediction with your health? Or the result of an experiment? Let's discover that together.

[Intro music plays]

Alex: Welcome back to the VUS podcast, a series initiated by the outreach efforts of the Atlas of Variant Effects alliance. I'm Alex, a professor at the University of Toronto, and today the team, Evelina, Adrine, Moez, Kortni and I will walk you through how artificial intelligence, or AI, is increasingly playing a role in clinical genetics.

Computers are now learning the language of life: decoding our DNA and giving it meaning. These algorithms can use this language to predict the three-dimensional structures of proteins at record speed - a problem once thought to be impossible. And so if computers can understand our genetic language, does this mean that they can also act as 'spell checkers' and identify which genetic mutations are incompatible with our healthy lives?

Today, our two hosts Adrine and Kortni will guide you through the development of variant effect predictors. We'll discover why scientists in this field are excited, but moving cautiously, when it comes to the use of these predictors in the clinic.

As always, we would like to note that this podcast focuses on a realistic portrayal of the basic and translational research behind rare diseases with the hope that it will lead to better patient care, but this podcast is not meant to be medical advice.

Adrine De Souza: Hi, I am Adrine.

Kortni Kindree: And I'm Kortni, today we will go on a deep dive on the power of AI in genomics.

Adrine: But first we need to understand a bit more about variant effect predictors, or VEPs. VEPs are computational algorithms that estimate variant function or pathogenicity. Some predict pathogenicity as a yes or no or "black box" and others are more nuanced. They give scores on a spectrum.

Kortni: VEPs are essential in investigating human variants, especially rare substitutions that may have never been classified before. With the increasing number of clinical testing, it is expected that many never-before-seen variants will be detected soon. Importantly, the use of VEPs does not require scientists to do any experiments to characterize the effect of these variants.

Adrine: There are two main classes of VEPs, fundamental and metapredictors. Earlier predictors used fundamental knowledge like physical-chemical properties of proteins to classify variants. But eventually their performance plateaued. And then metapredictors were developed, incorporating predictions of already existing VEPs into their classification models. These days, classifiers now use artificial intelligence, or AI, to learn about a system, find discriminatory properties, and then predict the outcomes of new variants.

Kortni: Computational classifiers are developed using a framework that generally involves 3 steps. The first, being developing a training set, followed by the detection of common features in this training set, and finally, the validation of performance, which is also called benchmarking. The problem is that every new predictor claims they performed better than all the previous ones. So, how can we know which ones to trust? And how do they compare to experiments like MAVEs?

Adrine: In this episode, we welcome two computational biologists that have made significant contributions to the advancements of variant effect predictors and can answer these questions for us.

Kortni: First, we welcome Dr. Debbie Marks, whose lab developed several computer software for understanding how proteins work. She used evolution to predict the effect of

mutations. Thank you Dr. Marks for joining us today, can you please begin by introducing yourself?

DM: Hi, my name is Debbie Marks, and I am a professor at Harvard Medical School in the Department of Systems Biology. I only do computation mathematics. I don't do any other kinds of experiments, and my background is math and computation. But I have a secret background from a long time ago, having sort of failed as a medic first time round in the seventies. And so I've had the lab for about 10 years, and we're driven to try and use computational biology to solve problems that are really hard to do by experiment.

Kortni: One of the areas you are heavily interested in are the use of 'large language models' in biology. So is this like ChatGPT but for biology?

DM: Oh, it's a great question. I mean, it's a very confused area, isn't it? So it's not like we're trying to imitate natural intelligence. It's like we're trying to use it to find patterns that we can't find with our own brains. But there is a more fundamental language of life than languages that we speak, and that's biological languages. Let's say, DNA, RNA, proteins and that language of life, I think we're still working on decoding and understanding and being able to predict, and being able to design. It's a very exciting time.

So in terms of large language models, I think they were honed on and do completely amazing things with human language that's spoken, written. And we know text to text, image, text, image, and text to text, and all the different combinations. But we don't yet know how good it's going to be to be able to crack open the things that we really want to solve in biology, whether it's in clinical medicine eventually, or it's in sustainability, or it's just, understanding biology.

We're still at the beginning, I think of making models for that. And I think large language models are, they're called large, really, because, you know, lots of stuff went into it. [laughs] And then there are lots of parameters, and I've heard quite a few people boasting about how many billions they've got this week. And it's not clear, actually, in biology whether that's going to work all the time, that bigger is better. And it's also not clear that whether or not how we represent the information in biology. So I think we have a way to go, which means this is really exciting.

Kortni: This podcast focuses mostly on variant effect maps and how multiplexed assays can determine the mutations that cause genetic diseases. ChatGPT had a famous case where it couldn't actually understand the word 'strawberry' having 3 'R's, despite having very good

grammar and lacking spelling mistakes in the text that it produces. So how can biologists use AI for understanding these ‘misspellings’ in our genome and determine the variant effect?

DM: Another great question. So I think that when we say variant effect, it's up to us, isn't it? To say variant effect on what? So if we mean “if I change this letter or this combination of letters in my DNA or my protein”, and how that changes the enzyme activity. That might be one thing. If I say, “if I change this letter or combinations, and how does it change the severity of a disease”? That's a different thing. How does it change thermal stability in a fermenter? You know, I think that one of the things is left off that sentence is the key thing, because different predictors and different models and different data going in the models will have advantages for different kinds of prediction. But I'm a very strong believer in prediction and design.

Kortni: So then, are VEPs sort of like black boxes? Because how would a clinician know what the VEP is actually trained on, especially if all the VEPs are trained on different things? How could they interpret the scores and determine whether you have a disease?

DM: Again, I think we have a responsibility to build models in biology that are as transparent as possible, and that are as interpretable as possible, and that have some connection to how robust they are. So some symbols, some annotation that says how confident we are in the result! Otherwise it's much less usable. And so I do think that's true in other domains, but it's especially true when it comes to people's health and the climate.

Kortni: With this in mind, can you tell us a little bit about EVE, the computer software your lab designed? How did this all come together?

DM: When we first looked at designing LLMs for predicting variant effects, we were *really* excited. And we started a long time ago!

Adrine: LLMs are ‘large language models’, essentially a form of artificial intelligence that is tasked to recognize patterns in language.

DM: And I thought, well, the first thing we could look at is, can you actually predict the effect on it? Say, a human protein in your body or mine? Can we say how likely that is to have some

bad or good effect? On one scale by looking at deep evolution, by looking at the same protein in a fish and in a worm and in a chicken.

Well, that sounds bonkers, doesn't it? [laughs] But we'd already learned that sequences across evolution contain information about millions and billions of experiments that have been done over time. And so it's very rich about context. And it turns out there are some models, you know, if you think about it? There are models that people used in the eighties, implicitly. "Oh, look at hemoglobin! Oh, my goodness, look at that residue there in haemoglobin. Oh, my goodness, that's gonna be bad! Nobody else that's walking on 2 feet, or is a mammal has got that!" You know, and this is the way it's moved forward. And I think one of the breakthroughs there was to think about context. And that's why we developed couplings, which is looking at pairwise dependencies. In the beginning, of course, we do the whole context now, but that in itself was very powerful. And so the story of Eve was quite funny, actually, because we'd already got a body of work where we said, if you use evolutionary information it's surprising and amazing how much you can be accurate in a mutation effect prediction. And that was very exciting!

Kortni: More accurate than MAVEs?

DM: In a way, if you think about those experiments that people do in the lab, the MAVEs which I love, of course. But if you think about them, all of them are proxies for something. Let's do this iron channel because we want to understand the likelihood of epilepsy. And in other words, the assay is a prediction on the phenotype in the human. And so we thought, well, why are we trying to predict the assay? If the assay isn't what we want eventually. And so we said, okay, now, let's say, imagine there is a measure, some clinical effect. And now we compare the Eve model, now, let's compare that directly to the clinical effect. And now let's take the deep mutational scans and compare those. And it turns out that for many proteins and many things that you actually can predict just as well as the experiments predict.

And that was a shock [laughs] to the world and to us a little bit how accurate they were. Not that accurate for the clinician, but accurate compared to doing an assay in a lab which may be measuring something which is just a proxy for something else. And the proxy isn't always clinical.

Kortni: You talked about context, and in a previous episode we discussed context in the sense of environmental influences on your body, but are these types of predictions also relevant in the non-disease context? Can variant effect predictors be used on something maybe a little less clinically relevant, like whether my lactose gene works or not?

DM: PopEve was kind of crazy, we thought. Oh, shoot! Oh, no, we've got the same problem everybody else has, which is, if I take one protein in your body or my body, and I do prediction. It's a very important protein. Let's call it important protein number one, right? And I do a prediction, and I get, you know, let's say it's minus one, if it's bad, and it's plus one, if it's great right?

And you know. it turns out that it's pretty good if you compare it to other to known clinical effects or mutational scanners. Pretty good. But now take another protein. Let's call it unimportant protein number 2, like a protein that maybe varies a lot. It varies a lot across people. Maybe apes don't have it, whatever it is, and maybe it's very free to mutate with very little phenotypic effect. And the range of the scores is the same. So what ends up happening, and this has happened, I'm sorry, this is a technical detail, but it's a really important one, and why we had to do the population part is because otherwise you will say something that is bad in one protein. But the protein might not be important for the body in any way that we know.

It might not be important to be able to go and swim in that lovely Caribbean sea or whatever it is may be important in another environment. Whereas others will be absolutely, if there's a mutation there, you basically, are not gonna survive. So it's very important to calibrate the scores against each other. So when people say they have proteome wide scores, they have the scores, but they are not relatable across the genes. And this is what we did with PopEve.

Kortni: So you said that MAVEs and variant effect predictors are about as good as each other at predicting clinical effects, but computer softwares get better, will they ever replace experiments entirely? I would suspect that MAVEs will also get better at this as well. Maybe there's a world where we can use both, or do enough MAVEs that predictors get really good at extrapolating these effects?

DM: I mean, that's an important question. And I'll circle back to what I said at the beginning there because if I want to predict how early somebody might get a neurodegenerative disease, I have to have a benchmark. I look at that. I can't just say, oh, I can predict that if I change this amino acid to that, the hairpin changes, you know. So the benchmark has to relate to the prediction and the claim. So I think that's really important. And so annotating those and actually then working with experimentalists to let's turn it all around now. Instead of us coming in after the effect, we should work altogether to design the experiments that are most important. One of the experiments we can design that everybody will get more out of. So we assume you believe that enough.

Adrine: This brings us to another set of stories. You heard that benchmarks are important, because, just like students, AI models are tested with exams. And it is getting harder to develop exams that can tease apart their differences. You can imagine that designing exams in school would be challenging if every student used ChatGPT! One area that ChatGPT is especially poor at is symbolic reasoning, where, for example, irrelevant information is used inaccurately in logic. In some challenges, ChatGPT performs much worse than children. So for variant effect predictors how do we build exams? To get at this, we talked to an expert in testing variant effect predictors. Hello Dr. Marsh, can you please introduce yourself before we start talking about variant effect predictors?

JM: Hi, I'm Joe Marsh. I'm a professor of computational protein biology at the University of Edinburgh, and a MRC Investigator at the MRC Human Genetics unit.

Adrine: Thank you, I think it'll be useful for people to have some idea of the early predictors - what did people use and what were your experiences with them?

JM: When it came time to start my own group at the University of Edinburgh, what I wanted to do was try and build on that kind of fundamental understanding of proteins that we had to try and use it for the interpretation of human genetic variation. And, in particular, thinking about how the ways that proteins assemble into complexes could be useful for understanding the molecular mechanisms that underlie disease mutations.

And that's really when I started being exposed to variant effect predictors, where like these computational tools that people were using to score variants, and people seemed to use them quite commonly, you know, when they'd have a variant they'd list the SIFT score, the Polyphen score. And they there was a lot of variability in how much trust people put in them. You know they were useful for prioritization, but no one really believed that they were totally predictive of pathogenicity. And so we started thinking more about these. And we started noticing because we're really interested in gain of function and dominant negative mutations, that they often didn't seem to perform very well for those mutations specifically.

Adrine: So dominant negative mutations are genetic mutations that cause abnormal proteins that interfere with the normal function of the wild-type protein. I guess newer predictors that use neural networks and multiple sequencing alignment probably did better on these variants right?

JM: You know, all these methods were being published. Papers were saying, this new predictor is the best predictor. This new predictor is the best predictor, but there seemed to be little consistency from one paper to the next.

Kortni: Let's say you're reading a new paper on a variant effect predictor, and it claims to be the best so far, you're probably thinking: "but what did they actually test this on?" Well it turns out, most papers actually use different metrics to evaluate their performance.

JM: We started to think about what is the best way of understanding what are the best predictors and to what extent we can trust their outputs. And we had this idea that we could use MAVE data as kind of an independent benchmark to assess the performance of the predictors. And it wasn't a totally novel idea. A few people had done it before on a very small scale.

Adrine: So we can't really tell if a predictor is truly doing better, how did MAVEs help assess the performance?

JM: I guess what we really did differently then is my PhD student at the time, Ben Livesey, I said, go out in the literature and find as many of these DMS datasets as you can. I think this is before MAVE-DB was around, and also find scores for as many of these variant effect predictors as you can. Sometimes he had to figure out how to run people's tools, using this MAVE-based benchmark to provide an independent way of scoring the performance of these variant effect predictors. Which really got a lot which really overcame a lot of the issues of what we call circularity associated with their evaluation.

Adrine: Circularity is the concept of using variants in the performance test that were also used to train the model, making it very biased towards precise predictions. How does benchmarking get around this phenomenon?

JM: There's dozens of new variant effect predictors being released every year, and if you look at those predictors, the papers describing them, nearly every single one will show some sort of comparison where they say we are the best compared to everything else. And obviously it's impossible that every new method is the best. And I think there's a number of things going on there, but at the simplest, people are probably just picking the benchmarks that make themselves

look the best, you know, whether they're purposely cheating or just sort of subconsciously tuning their benchmark.

They they do it in a way where they make themselves look good. And so the take home from that is, we really can't trust what people say about their own models, because people are always going to overinflate the performance of their own models. So the I think the power of what we've been doing is providing an independent benchmark, so assessing it in an independent way. And I think part of the reason why people have trusted us is that we're also not trying to push our own variant effect predictor because we're not making variant effect predictors. We don't really have any skin in the game, we're, you know, just trying to do a fair, unbiased assessment of these existing approaches.

Kortni: These independent benchmarks have existed previously for many other fields where predictors played a large role. For example, the CASP community (or Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction community), has been challenging predictors of protein structures for years by experimentally producing crystal structures, hiding the true results, and then asking the team to produce their best prediction of the protein structure. Ever since 2018, this competition has been won by sophisticated neural networks and has led to the recent Nobel prize in structural predictions. But coming back to variants of uncertain significance.

Adrine: The fact that humans have labelled pathogenic and benign variants also include our own biases to the problem right? If the label given used some knowledge about protein structure or function this should also create circularity. So how do MAVEs play into this?

JM: Now, the power of the MAVE data specifically comes down to how these a lot of these models are generated. So a lot of them are trained on labeled data sets of known pathogenic and benign variants. And so they'll use some sort of machine learning algorithm to come up with the optimal discrimination between pathogenic and benign. But models become very biased by the data on which they're trained. So they'll do good on data that they've been directly trained on, or that's closely related to what they've been trained on. They'll also look good on different variants from the same genes that were used in the training, or even evolutionarily related genes are used in the testing that were used in training. And these kinds of things can creep into these assessments using traditional sort of pathogenic versus benign benchmarks that confound fair assessment of predictor performance.

Adrine: And how MAVEs can help?

JM: So the power of the MAVEs, the deep mutational scanning is that it's totally independent of how humans have classified variants. It's independent experimental measurements. And so, although these MAVEs may not always be perfectly reflective of pathogenicity, the power is that they're just a fair, independent measurement of variant effect. And really, by combining lots of different MAVEs. We've found that it seems to be able to give us a fair assessment of relative predictor performance that does seem to correlate very strongly with how well these methods actually do on traditional prediction of disease mutations.

Adrine: Is this now the main reason to do MAVEs? Are scientists just becoming 'slaves' to the data crunchers?

JM: So in terms of how experimentalists should think about this, you know, I don't think anyone should be doing their MAVEs just because they want to provide data for benchmarking. There's so many valuable reasons to do a MAVE in terms of understanding your individual systems. But it's a valuable side effect of doing a MAVE is that we get this data that can be used in the benchmark.

Adrine: So experimentalists do MAVEs for honorable reasons and it looks like as a side-effect, we help in the benchmarking of VEPs, as well. So I guess we get this for free.

JM: And, in fact, an important thing about our strategy is that we don't really care that much about what the MAVE is measuring. Because there's different kinds of experimental phenotypes that you can measure within a MAVE, and you can imagine that some might be much better for predicting pathogenicity than others.

Adrine: So even if the predictors become better than experiments, is it still important to have experimental data to truly assess the performance of these algorithms?

JM: But our approach has been that as long as these experiments have some relationship to fitness, then they're still useful in our combined benchmark that brings everything together. So I guess I guess the point is, no matter what you're measuring, it can still probably be useful for

benchmarking in some way. The most important thing is just making your data available. And especially depositing it in MAVE-DB. So like I said, we used to have to do a huge amount of work of searching the literature for these data sets to include. But now that's gotten a lot easier for us because we just go to MAVE-DB and get 90% of the data included in our latest benchmark. So by making things freely available and easily discoverable. It greatly benefits this kind of independent, benchmarking.

Adrine: Can you tell us what's one thing you've learned from benchmarking VEPs that maybe caution their wide use in the clinical setting?

JM: There's a lot of interest and push to make these variant effect predictors count as more when it comes to making genetic diagnoses. But there's a lot of people pushing right now to say, okay, let's set a threshold for this predictor, and that means this is strong evidence of pathogenicity. And on one hand, it's admirable, because I think there's a lot of potential for these tools to improve diagnosis. But at the same time, we need to be extremely careful about this, because, as I mentioned, a lot of these approaches for benchmarking lead to inflated performance because they're not accounting for issues related to data circularity.

Adrine: Is there a chance that our actual knowledge of disease will get corrupted if these VEPs gain mainstream use in the clinic?

JM: There's another problem that comes along with this in that once we start using these predictors as evidence for making genetic diagnoses. Well, the thing is that variant, then, is going to be put in the publicly available databases like ClinVar, which is the database where people put pathogenic and benign variants. And so, if you use a variant effect predictor as evidence to call something pathogenic, then you put that variant in ClinVar. Well, then, the next generation of predictors are going to start being trained on that variant which got its classification on the basis of a variant effect predictor. So it confounds the training of future models, and it confounds the fair testing of future models.

Kortni: People have noticed that a lot of text on the internet is now being generated by AI such as ChatGPT, and future versions of ChatGPT will be trained on its own text. So with all these caveats, you might be wondering... should you ever trust a variant effect predictor? Will you always want an experiment to back up the prediction? Computer scientists in this field are well-aware of these issues, and they urge caution.

DM: I think this has built up over the years over 20-30 years a lot of cynicism which is understandable from clinicians. The burden of proof is on us, because otherwise we're going to end up causing 10 years of a lot of heartache in in people's experimental time. People have what I call the sausage factory, which is, throw everything in, you know. ATAC-seq, CHIP-seq, GTEx, everything! All the UK Biobank, all evolution. And let's what see what comes out. And if you're lucky, it's a sausage right? And I think that what we have to do is think about what we need and what we want to find out.

Kortni: But all is not gloom in this field. There's actually a lot of excitement ahead and a strong sense of optimism that things will change and will be much better in the future.

DM: Oh, I think this is going to change hugely in the next 10 years. I mean, at the moment we can read DNA, and we can write DNA. But you know, can we design from it? Can we do something to perturb it with any confidence? Very little. I think it is going to affect clinical practice. I think the lowest hanging fruit in that is going to be early detection of cancer, vaccine design for pandemic threats. Things that are low cost, so I think that it will change in the next few years.

Adrine: Thank you so much!

Alex: Thank you for joining us today. In this episode, we saw how scientists are developing the “ChatGPT” of variant effects, how “exams” are created to test them, and what their current pitfalls are. Personally, as a scientist working on producing experimental datasets, progress in this area will probably never quench this desire to verify with an experiment and more importantly, to provide understanding about the laws of human cell biology. That being said, variant effect predictors will likely very soon be part of the scientific process and I can see a future where they play a large role in the clinic.

This episode really only scratched the surface of what is possible with AI in the field of medicine. What about wearable devices that can monitor your health in real time? What about automatic development of vaccine antigens and drugs for specific targets? This will have to wait for another episode. But until then, now is the time for the rapid fire questions!

[Rapid fire questions]

Moez Dawood: Are you ready?

JM: Okay, yep.

Moez: DNA or RNA?

DM: Both.

JM: DNA.

Moez: R or Python?

DM: Python

JM: Pearl

Moez: Short-read or Long-read?

DM: Long.

JM: Long!

Moez: Single-Cell or Bulk?

DM: Both.

JM: Single.

Moez: Knock-in or Knock-out?

DM: Both.

JM: Knock-in definitely.

Moez: Golden Gate or Gibson?

DM: Don't know.

JM: Golden Gate.

Moez: Coding or Noncoding?

DM: Both.

JM: Coding.

Moez: *In vitro* or *in vivo*?

DM: *In vivo*.

JM: *In vitro*.

Moez: Favorite model organism?

DM: Humans.

JM: E. coli.

Moez: Favorite scientist?

DM: Random human

JM: Jacques Monod.

Moez: Favorite media?

JM: LB

Moez: Favorite sequencing technology?

JM: Sanger

Moez: Favorite piece of lab equipment?

DM: Computer.

JM: Autoclave.

Moez: Favorite science movie/media?

DM: Oh its got to be three-body problem.

JM: Jurassic Park.

Moez: Something outside the lab that you wish you could multiplex?

DM: Having children.

JM: Getting kids ready for school and nursery in the morning.

Moez: What is the smartest thing you've ever done in the lab?

DM: Folded a protein from its sequence.

JM: Transitioned from wet-lab into computational research.

Moez: What is the stupidest thing you've ever done in the lab?

DM: I swear, I do it every day.

JM: I once dumped a tub of dry LB powder on my head. It was on the top shelf.

Moez: [laughs] That's awesome.

Alex: To all you listeners, I hope you enjoyed today's episode, and don't forget to tune in for the next episodes on Variants and Us, where we'll discuss clinical variant databases.

[Outro music plays]